

Quantum Features from Time-Independence of Impulse Balance in the Photon Reflection/Refraction Problem Part II

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In Part I, we noted that a photon number balance equation, which is equivalent to an energy balance equation, written in terms of fluxes describes all of the information in a photon steady state reflection/refraction problem in one dimension. We also pointed out that one equation cannot solve for two unknowns and suggested that because all information is contained in the classical photon count equation, one may break it into two equations (quantum balance equations for probability and average impulse) in order to solve the problem. Thus the two quantum equations are needed to solve the problem, but collapse into the classical conservation of photon number equation.

In this note, we argue that in classical mechanics there are two different, but consistent descriptions of force acting on a particle. The first is impulse $\int dt F = \Delta p$ where p is momentum. Two particles with the same momentum, but different velocities, create the same physical impulse. In other words, time is removed (integrated out) in this picture.

An equivalent formalism is to write $dt = dx/v$ or $F dx = v dp$. This form breaks the degeneracy of p 's with different velocities. In other words, time is important.

Thus we argue that at the classical level there are two equivalent formalisms. The impulse one does not consider time, while the work-kinetic energy one does. Both are legitimate.

For the reflection-refraction of photons in one dimension, both formalisms should apply and lead to consistent results as do the impulse and kinetic energy-work approaches. The latter uses time and is equivalent to three ideas: photon number conservation, energy conservation and pressure conservation, all three being associated with time. The concept of impulse, however, suggests that one should be able to consider space in terms of impulse alone and not time i.e. not velocity. This forces one to introduce a complex probability associated with impulse hits i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. This probability and its corresponding average impulse balance yield two independent equations, while the photon count conservation only supplies one. Thus the problem needs to be solved using impulse formalism, even though it is completely consistent with count conservation.

The form $\exp(ipx)$ leads to new physics (when compared with classical physics) as it suggests interference pattern results.

Impulse and Work in Classical Physics

Both the ideas of impulse and work exist in classical physics and are consistent with each other i.e.

Impulse = $\int dt F = \Delta p$ (momentum) ((1a)) and Work = $\int F dx = \int v dp$ ((1b))

A key difference between the two is the presence of time (or speed) in ((1b)). In other words, two particles may have the same momentum, but different velocities. From ((1a)) they have the same impulse i.e. are indistinguishable in the impulse formalism, but from ((1b)) they have different velocities and are distinguishable.

Which picture is correct? Both are correct, even in the quantum mechanics of a free particle. A quantum free particle moves with a certain speed and so time is physical. Its impulse on a target, however, is associated with its momentum, not speed. Furthermore its 2-slit interference pattern (etc) is also speed (i.e. time) independent. Thus there are certain observations which require the notion of time and others which do not, but both are physical and consistent with each other.

As a result, when examining a quantum free particle problem, both approaches should apply and should lead to consistent results. In previous notes, we suggested that the impulse picture is more suitable to quantum mechanics, as bound states consist of wavefunctions $W(x) = \sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Furthermore, a photon reflection-refraction problem also requires an impulse picture for its solution, but this is because the time picture leads to only one independent equation, not two. Thus the time picture is not incorrect, it is just that looking at the reflection-refraction problem in terms of pressure, like one does in a classical statistical mechanical gas, does not solve it.

Conservation of Photon Number, Energy and Pressure

In the above section, we discussed the impulse picture with no time present and the work picture with time present. We suggested that both are physically legitimate. We begin by considering the one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem in terms of the time picture.

A photon with energy pc moves in the x direction in a medium with an index of refraction $n_1=1$ and strikes a surface along the y direction with n_2 .

The number of reflected and refracted photons add to the number of incident photons. This equation may be written in terms of fluxes: AA , BB , CC for the incident, reflected and refracted photons. AA/c is the number of photons etc. Thus:

$$AA/c = BB/c + CC/c_2 \quad \text{where } c_2=c/n \quad ((2))$$

Given that the energy of the incident, reflected and refracted photons is the same, one may multiply ((2)) by e to obtain a non-independent energy conservation equation. This we argue is the real problem with the time picture. A conservation of photon number and energy are nonindependent equations. If one brings BB/c to the LHS in ((2)) and multiplies by $e=pc=p_2c_2$, then one has a pressure balance equation which again makes use of the concept of time i.e. AA is a flux multiplied by p , an impulse etc, but again this is not an independent equation.

Due to the non-independence of the photon count and energy equations, one cannot solve for the two unknowns B,C in terms of A .

Impulse Picture

As noted in the first paragraph, one has both a time dependent and a non-time dependent impulse picture. The latter only produces one equation which does not solve the problem. What happens if one considers the problem from the point of view of impulses i.e. time does not matter?

From classical physics one knows that the impulse and work-time pictures must be consistent. Two particles with the same momentum, but different velocities have the same impulse, but travel through space at different rates. The impulse picture removes time so one is not interested in the rate at which the particle travels through space. Space, however, still exists and p , impulse, is a key quantity. One needs a picture in space which distinguishes between p values, but is consistent with the time picture which indicates that all x points have the same weight. A result which allows for this situation is to have a smooth velocity, but a complex periodic impulse hit probability pattern in space i.e.

$\exp(ipx)$ ((3))

((3)) maps to 1 i.e. $\exp(ipx)\exp(-ipx) = 1$. No time is present in ((3)) and one may actually solve a photon reflection-refraction problem, which does have physical speeds and time present, in terms of a no-time scenario i.e.

- (A) A balance of probability ((3))- otherwise it would need to be created or destroyed
- (B) A balance of average impulse

(A) and (B) lead to independent equations which allow one to solve the reflection/refraction problem, whereas photon count/energy/pressure balance does not. This, we argue, suggests that impulse hits are key to describing how quantum free particles interact.

Thus: $A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip^2 x)$ ((4a)) at $x=0$

$A p \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = C p^2 \exp(ip^2 x)$ ((4b)) at $x=0$

((4a)) and ((4b)) may be solved for B,C in terms of A. They may also be multiplied together to yield the single equation of count/energy/pressure balance.

Physically it is known that impulse on a target is not dependent on velocity if the momentum is constant i.e. $p=m_1v_1=m_2v_2$ create the same impulse. Also a two slit experiment etc does not depend on speed, but rather momentum only. It is at least feasible that one consider the reflection-refraction problem in terms of impulse with no present, even though physically there is speed and time in the picture. It just does not physically impact the way interactions occur. This we argue is why the energy conservation equation obtained by multiplying a photon count equation by e does not distinguish between the different impulses p , $-p$ and p^2 . They are all treated as having the same energy, which they do. There is nothing unphysical about this,

except that it leads to the idea of pressure i.e. $p c$ instead of impulse alone. Physically it seems that impulse is the key to solving the problem even though a pressure balance equation follows from ((2)) (when BB/c is brought to the LHS and the equation multiplied by $p c$ on the LHS and $p^2 c^2$ on the RHS). Thus pressure balance is not wrong, it just does not describe the interaction fully. It gives no more information than photon count balance.

Two Equations, Two Unknowns

To solve for two unknowns in a linear type equation, one needs two independent equations. These two equations may be multiplied together to create a single equation, but this single equation has somehow lost some information in the sense that one may not solve for the two unknowns. One may, however, recover the lost information by breaking the single equation into two instead of looking for a second independent equation.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in classical mechanics there are two consistent pictures. The first is the non-time dependent impulse: $\Delta p = \int F dt$ which depends only on momentum. Two particles with the same p , but different v , create the same physical impulse. This may be extended in quantum mechanics to stating that they create the same impulse and the same diffraction/interference patterns. Thus even though velocity and hence time are physically present, they may not control the interaction it seems. (We apply this idea to one dimensional reflection/refraction).

The second picture is the time present work picture or energy conservation: $v dp = F dx$. Both pictures are consistent in classical mechanics.

If one considers a one dimensional photon reflection-refraction problem from the point of view of time present (which is not incorrect), one has a balance of photon numbers i.e. using fluxes: $AA/c = BB/c + CC/c^2$ where $c^2 = c/n^2$ and A, B, C refer to the incident, reflected and refracted photons. Multiplying by e yields conservation of energy. Bringing BB/c to the LHS and multiplying the LHS by $p c$ and the RHS by $p^2 c^2$ yields pressure balance. These are not incorrect equations, they are just not independent of the conservation of photon count equation. Thus one cannot solve for B, C in terms of A . Classical physics suggests, however, that one may also consider impulses and that this picture should be consistent with the time one.

A big change from classical physics is that given smooth constant velocity motion which suggests each x has the same weight, one moves to an impulse picture in space in which different p values in space yield different physical impulse hits. One must distinguish between p values in x , yet at the same time have smooth equally weighted x points. The solution is to use $\exp(ipx)$ as an impulse hit probability. In the time removed picture, one does not have a smooth x picture, but rather $\exp(ipx)$, which is a probability. One has again two equations, a balance of $\exp(ipx)$ s and a balance of $p \exp(ipx)$ s i.e. average impulse. In this case, the two equations are independent and the problem may be solved i.e. $A \exp(ipx) + B \exp(-ipx) = C \exp(ip^2 x)$ and $p A \exp(ipx) - p B \exp(-ipx) = p^2 C \exp(ip^2 x)$ at $x=0$. These two equations may be multiplied together to yield the photon count balance equation i.e the two approaches are consistent. The fact that the impulse approach solves the problem suggests that the impulse mechanism with no time

present describes interactions of quantum free particles even though a pressure balance equation exists. It unfortunately is not independent of the photon count balance equation.